

Students Behaviour Towards Online Shopping: A Case Study in Higher Education Institutions of Lakhimpur District of Assam

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ABSTRACT

The growth of internet technology has significantly influenced consumer online shopping behaviour worldwide. Online shopping, a form of e-commerce facilitates the purchase of goods and services via the internet. This study, data has been collected by using a simple random sampling method from higher education students at Madhabdev University in the Lakhimpur District of Assam. The research aimed to examine the relationship between students' age group, income, and educational level with internet use. Additionally, it sought to identify popular online shopping platforms and products, influencing factors, and challenges encountered by students regarding online shopping. The present study indicated a significant positive correlation between students' age group and internet use, income and internet use, and educational level and internet use. This study found that most respondents were highly influenced by factors such as time saving, offers and discounts, money saving, shopping enjoyment, safety and security, and efficient delivery systems. However, respondents also reported various challenges, including prolonged delivery times, visual discrepancies between product pictures and received goods, difficulty contacting sellers, and receiving damaged or incorrect goods.

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KEYWORDS: Internet, E-commerce, online shopping, Higher education, Students' Behaviour

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent time, The internet is popular networks for doing any activities like communicate with others (email, social media, messaging), sharing and exchange of ideas (online courses, tutorials, webinars), information (daily regional, national and international news, gathering data), entertainment (online gaming, streaming, videos), commerce (online shopping, banking, transaction), Information retrieval (search engines, websites, online libraries) etc. in the world. The advancement of internet technology has profoundly impacted global business (Farah et al., 2018)¹. The emergence of the internet has transformed business methods, making online shopping popular due to its practical strengths (Kuswanta et al., 2019)². The internet has picked up the states of an enthusiastic financially savvy stage over a rich wellspring of correspondence (Sreekanth et al., 2020)³. The internet is being developed rapidly since last two decades, and with relevant digital economy that is driven by information technology also being developed worldwide (Jukariya and Singhvi, 2018)⁴. E-commerce can be thought of as an activity wherein the consumer uses the internet to order a product or

services (Vaidya and Vaidya, 2017)⁵. Online shopping (e-retail or e-shopping) is a form of electronic commerce which allows consumers to directly buy goods or services from a seller over the internet using a web browser (Jukariya and Singhvi, 2018)⁴. Online shopping is a virtual shopping that enables consumers to shop across multiple market places on a 24x7 basis through the internet (Sreekanth et al., 2020)¹. Online shopping gained momentums due to a variety of reasons, viz. convenience, availability of products at consumers doorsteps, gift vouchers, discounts and low price, variety of product etc. (Sreekanth et al., 2020)¹.

According to the Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI) annual report 2022-23, approximately 346 million Indians engage in online transactions such as e-commerce and digital payments. India ranks as the second-largest market globally in terms of internet users, after China. The number of active internet users in India has consistently increased in both urban and rural areas over recent years. According to economictimes.com, internet users in India grew from 574 million (41% of the total population) in 2019, with 309 million in urban and 264 million in rural areas, to 821 million

(55% of the total population) in 2023, comprising 378 million urban and 442 million rural users. The IAMAI report 2022-23 estimated that internet users in India would reach up to 900 million by 2025. This widespread internet access and increased e-commerce usage by traders have led to massive growth in online shopping in recent years (Choudhury and Dey)⁶. A Statista.com report from 2023 indicates that the highest online internet user rate globally was among the 15 to 24 age group. Therefore, this paper investigates "Higher Education Students Behaviour towards Online Shopping: A case study in Lakhimpur District of Assam".

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dalafrooz et al. (2010) found that consumers who buy goods and services online benefit significantly from convenience, price, and item selection. Their study also indicated a positive effect of utilitarian orientation on attitudes toward online shopping, while hedonic orientation had no significant effect. Similarly, convenience, price, and wider selection were significantly and positively associated with attitudes toward online shopping, whereas customer service, fun, and hedonic personality showed no significant association.

Choudhury and Dey (2014) reported that 90.5% of respondents shopped online, while 9.5% did not. Books were the most purchased items (31.5%), followed by apparel (20.5%) and electronic goods. Their study revealed a significant relationship between gender, internet literacy, and online product price with online shopping, but no significant relationship with education and website usability.

Vaidya and Vaidya (2017), in their study "Online Shopping Trends among College Students," found that 55% of respondents preferred mobile apps for online shopping. Flipkart was the most preferred platform, followed by Amazon, with electronic items and clothes being the most frequently purchased products. Cash on Delivery (COD) was the preferred mode of payment for most respondents during online shopping.

Jukariya and Singhvi (2018) identified transaction security, multiple payment options, product price, quality, personal privacy, security, speed of access, and after-sales services as major factors influencing students' online purchases.

Farah et al. (2018), in their "Online Shopping Behaviour Among University Students: Case Study of MUST University," found that 99.0% of MUST university students engaged in online shopping, with computers, electronics, and mobile phones being the most purchased items. They also noted that functionality, trust, privacy, firm reputation, and perceived value were common factors influencing consumer online buying behavior.

Kuswanta et al. (2019) stated that enjoyment, perceived risk, and social influence positively affected students' behavior toward online shopping, while online advertisements, website quality, trust, and security did not. They found that fashion products (47%) were the most purchased by students,

followed by electronic items (19.3%), skincare, accessories, internet and mobile credit, and household needs.

Parameswari and Saravanan (2019) observed that male respondents predominantly preferred electronic products, while females preferred cosmetic products online. Ninety percent of respondents purchased products online once a month or every two months. Sixty percent spent 2 to 5 hours daily on the internet, and 25% spent more than 5 hours. Amazon was the top preferred website for online purchases, followed by Flipkart, e-Bay, Myntra, ShopClues, and Jabong. They also noted that online marketing met customer requirements, and customers felt secure regarding money transactions and refunds.

Sreekanth et al. (2020) identified delivery time as the most crucial factor influencing students' decisions to buy goods and services online, followed by company reputation, quality, advertisement, privacy, offers and discounts, trust, guarantees and warranties, and low price. They also reported a positive relationship between gender and delivery time in online shopping behavior.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To test the relationship between students' age group & internet use, income & internet use and educational level & internet use in the study area.
2. To identify the most popular platforms and products with respect to online shopping among higher education studying students in the study area.
3. To what extent do various online shopping factors influence the purchasing behavior of higher education students?
4. To ascertain if students in higher education have encountered different challenges while shopping online.

4. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

- A. Sample: The present study, sample was collected from newly formed Madhabdev University in Lakhimpur District of Assam.
- B. Sampling method: simple random sampling has been used.
- C. Sample size: 96 samples have been collected through field study.
- D. Data sources: Primary data for the study was gathered using a high quality, well-structured questionnaire. The researcher used secondary data for obtained ideas, information from existing research reports, journals, and surveys about higher education students' online buying habits.

5. HYPOTHESIS

- H_0 : There is no correlation between students' age and duration of internet use.

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- H_0 : There is no correlation between monthly income of the family and internet use of the students’.
- H_0 : There is no correlation between level of education of the students and internet use.

6. ANALISYS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1: Relation between students’ age group and internet use

Age group	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)	Average internet use of daily (in hours)
Below 18	4	4.2	4.5
19-24	79	82.3	5.48
25-30	7	7.3	7
30 above	6	6.3	6.2

Source: Field study

It has been seen that 82.3 percent respondents are age group between 19 to 24 years and followed 7.3 percent, 6.3 percent and 4.2 percent by the age group 25 to 30, 30 years above and below 18 years students’ respectively. It has been found that the average internet use positively increases from the age group of below 18 to age group of 25-30, after which it decreases.

Null hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant correlation between students’ age group and duration of internet use, i.e., $\rho=0$.

The correlation coefficient (r) was found to be 0.1399, and the t-value was 1.38. Since the correlation value of t is greater than the tabulated value for 94d.f. at 5% level of significance, hence we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and may conclude that there is a significant correlation between students’ age group and duration of internet use.

Table 2: Relation between monthly income of the family and internet use

Monthly income of the family	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)	Average internet use of daily (in hours)
Below 25,000	42	43.8	4.56
25,001-50,000	20	20.8	5.7
50,001-75,000	11	11.8	6.09
75,001-1,00,000	10	10.8	6.12
1,00,000 above	13	13.5	6.16

Source: Field study

It has been found that as monthly income of the family increases the average internet use of the students’ increases. Null hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant correlation between monthly income of the family and internet use of the students’ i.e., $\rho=0$.

The correlation coefficient (r) value was found to be 0.176, and the t-value was 1.74. Since calculated value of t is greater than the tabulated value for 94d.f. at 5% level of significance, hence we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and we may conclude that there is a significant correlation between monthly income of the family and duration of internet use of the students’.

Table 3:Relation between educational level and internet use

Educational level	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)	Average internet use of daily (in hours)
UG	35	36.5	5.18
PG	55	57.3	5.51
Ph. D.	6	6.3	7

Source: Primary data

It has been seen that 57.3 percent respondents are obtained from PG level studying students’ and followed by UG and Ph. D. level studying students’ i.e., 36.5 and 6.3 percent respectively. It has been found that daily internet use by the

Ph.D. studying students’ is 7 hours on average and followed by 5.51 hours and 5.18 hours by the PG and UG studying students’.

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Null hypothesis (H₀): There is no correlation between educational level and internet use of the students’ i.e., $\rho=0$. The correlation coefficient (r) value was found to be 0.938 and the t-value was 26.238. Since calculated value of t is

greater than the tabulated value for 94d.f. at 5% level of significance, hence we reject the null hypothesis and we may conclude that there is a significant correlation between educational level and internet use of the students’.

Most popular online shopping platforms and products

Figure 1: Online shopping platforms

Source: Field study

A study found that 82.3 percent of respondents shop online from Flipkart, followed by Amazon at 9.4 percent and Myntra at 8.3 percent.

Figure 2: Most Popular Products in online

Source: Field study

It has been found that 57.3 percent respondents shop online for clothes, followed by books at 17.7 percent, electronic products at 13.5 percent, Fashion & beauty products at 7.3 percent, groceries at 2.1 percent, cosmetic & jewelers at 1 percent and Travelling & entertaining at 1 percent respectively.

Various factors that influence online shopping

The rapid advancement of digital technology has significantly transformed consumer behavior, particularly in the realm of

online shopping. With increasing internet penetration, improved logistics, and the convenience of digital shopping, more consumers are opting to shop online rather than in traditional brick-and-mortar stores. However, the decision to shop online is influenced by a variety of factors ranging from individual preferences and technological accessibility to economic, psychological, and social considerations. There have been seen that a lot of factors like time saving, offers & discount, money saving, 24*7 availability, shopping

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enjoyment, details description of the product, delivery system, return policy, price of the products, flexible to delivery system, safety & security, advertisement of the products etc. influence to the customer for online shopping.

Table 4 depicts the percentage of the respondents that influenced them to various factors while shopping goods services from online as follows:

Table 4: Percentage of the respondents that influenced them to various factors while shopping goods services

Sl. No	Factors	Extremely	Very	Somewhat	Slightly	Not	Total percentage
1	Time saving	34	34	18	12	2	100
2	Offers & discounts	29	38	23	5	5	100
3	Money saving	25	38	29	6	2	100
4	24*7 availability	42	34	18	5	1	100
5	Shopping enjoyment	28	39	25	4	4	100
6	Variety of the products available	36	40	16	7	1	100
7	Details description of the products	26	44	23	5	2	100
8	Price of the products	22	42	25	9	2	100
9	Advertisement of the products	24	39	28	5	4	100
10	Privacy protection	22	41	23	11	3	100
11	Delivery system	20	46	23	8	3	100
12	Shipping cost	18	48	26	5	3	100
13	Provides personal information	14	38	32	13	3	100
14	Return policy	27	47	18	3	5	100
15	Safety & security	19	44	30	5	2	100
16	Flexible to choose delivery system	24	39	23	9	5	100
17	Direct interaction with dealers	15	47	22	11	5	100
18	Comparing products	19	43	29	5	4	100
19	Availability of live customers	19	41	21	9	10	100

Source: Field study

Time saving: 34% of respondents reported being significantly influenced, with a notable proportion indicating they were either extremely or very influenced.

Offers & discount: The survey results show that 38% of respondents were extremely influenced, 29% were much influenced, and 23% were somewhat influenced, while 5% respondents reported slightly or no influenced.

Money saving: The survey revealed a notable trend, with 25% of respondents indicating extreme influence, 38% very influenced, 29% somewhat influenced, and smaller proportions reporting slight (6%) or no influence (2%).

24*7availability:The data revealed a strong impact, with 42% of respondents extremely influenced, 34% very influenced, and 18% somewhat influenced, and only 6% combined slight and no influence.

Shopping enjoyment: The data showed that 39% of respondents were very influenced, 28% extremely influenced, and 25% somewhat influenced, with only 8% combined slight and no influence.

Variety of the product available: A significant majority of respondents reported being influenced, with 40% very, 36% extremely, and 16% somewhat influenced, while a small minority (8%) indicated slight or no influence.

Details description of the products: The data showed that 44% of respondents were very influenced, 26% extremely influenced, and 23% somewhat influenced, with only 5% slightly and 2% not influenced.

Price of the products: The data indicated that 42% of respondents were much influenced 25% somewhat influenced and 22% extremely influenced, with 9% slightly and 2% not influenced.

Advertisement of the products: The data revealed that 39% of respondents were very influenced, 28% somewhat influenced, and 24% extremely influenced, with 5% slightly and 4% not influenced.

Privacy protection: The data showed that 41% of respondents were very influenced, 23% somewhat influenced, and 22% extremely influenced, with 11% slightly and 3% not influenced.

Delivery system: The survey results revealed that 46% of respondents were very influenced, 23% somewhat influenced, 20% extremely influenced, and smaller proportions were slightly (8%) or not influenced (3%).

Shipping cost: The survey results showed that 48% of respondents were very influenced, 26% somewhat influenced, 18% extremely influenced, and smaller proportions were slightly (5%) or not influenced (3%).

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Provides personal information: The data showed that 39% of respondents were very influenced, 32% somewhat influenced, and 14% extremely influenced, with 13% slightly and 3% not influenced.

Product return policy: The survey results revealed that 47% of respondents were very influenced, 27% extremely influenced, 18% somewhat influenced, and smaller proportions were not (5%) or slightly influenced (3%).

Safety & security: A notable proportion of respondents reported being influenced, with 44% very, 30% somewhat, and 19% extremely influenced, while a minority (7%) indicated slight or no influence.

Flexible to choose delivery system: The data indicated that 39% of respondents were very influenced, 24% extremely influenced, and 23% somewhat influenced, with 9% slightly and 5% not influenced.

Direct information with dealer: The survey results revealed that 47% of respondents were very influenced, 22% somewhat influenced, 15% extremely influenced, and smaller proportions were slightly (11%) or not influenced (5%).

Comparing products: The survey results indicated that 43% of respondents were very influenced, 29% somewhat

influenced, 19% extremely influenced, and smaller proportions were slightly (5%) or not influenced (4%).

Availability of live customer care: The data indicated that 41% of respondents were very influenced, 21% somewhat influenced, and 19% extremely influenced, with 10% not and 9% slightly influenced.

Problems faced on online shopping

In recent times, online shopping has revolutionized the way consumers purchase goods and services. With the growth of e-commerce platforms, people can now shop from the comfort of their homes, access a wide variety of products, and compare prices with ease. However despite its numerous benefits, online shopping also presents several challenges that affect the customer buying behavior. Common issues like difficulty to contact seller, delivery time change after transaction, received wrong goods, received damage goods, difficulty to change defective products, product guaranty is not assured, delivery time too long, complex process of order, privacy information to be given, visual difference picture & received goods, and confused by over choice etc have been seen on online shopping.

Figure 4 illustrates the percentage of the challenges faced by higher education students while shopping online as follows:

Source: Field study

From figure 4, it has been found that 65.63% respondent faced issues like confusion due to over choice while shopping from online and followed by 59.37% reporting delivery time too long, 58.33% experiencing visual difference picture and

received goods, 55.21% facing difficulty to contact seller and received damage goods respectively, 50% received wrong goods, 47.92% reported unassured product guarantees and concerns about privacy information, 45.83% faced difficulty

with defective products, 40.62% experienced delivery time change after transactions, 38.54% noted no after sales service and 26.04% encountered complex process of order.

7. FINDINGS

The average internet use positively increases with age from below 18 to 25-30 years, then decreases. The study also found that there is a significant correlation between students' age group and duration of internet use. It is also revealed that as monthly family income increases, students' average internet use also increases. Similarly, there is a significant correlation between monthly family income and students' duration of internet use. Additionally, it is also found that, Ph.D. students expend average 7 hours of daily internet use, followed by PG students (5.51 hours) and UG students (5.18 hours). There is a significant correlation between educational level and students' internet use. The study found that Flipkart is the most popular online shopping platform (82.3%), followed by Amazon (9.4%) and Myntra (8.3%). Clothes are the most frequently purchased online product (57.3%), followed by books (17.7%), electronic products (13.5%), fashion & beauty products (7.3%), groceries (2.1%), cosmetic & jewellery (1%), and travelling & entertaining (1%). Most respondents are significantly influenced by online shopping factors such as time saving, offers & discounts, money saving, 24/7 availability, shopping enjoyment, detailed product descriptions, delivery system, return policy, product price, flexible delivery system, safety & security, and product advertisements. Key challenges faced by respondents include confusion due to over-choice (65.63%), long delivery times (59.37%), visual differences between product pictures and received goods (58.33%), difficulty contacting sellers (55.21%), receiving damaged goods (55.21%), receiving wrong goods (50%), unassured product guarantee and privacy information concerns (47.92%), difficulty with defective products (45.83%), delivery time changes after transactions (40.62%), no after-sales service (38.54%), and complex order processes (26.04%).

8. CONCLUSION

The internet serves as a widely used network for various activities globally, including communication, information exchange, entertainment, commerce, and information retrieval. Online shopping is a primary form of e-commerce, enabling the global buying and selling of goods and services via the internet. This study reveals a significant correlation between students' age group and internet use, family income and internet use, and educational level and internet use. Flipkart is the preferred online shopping platform for most respondents, followed by Amazon and Myntra. Clothes are the most popular online purchase among respondents, followed by books, electronic goods, fashion & beauty products, and groceries. Higher education students are influenced by numerous factors while shopping online,

including time saving, offers & discounts, money saving, 24/7 availability, shopping enjoyment, detailed product descriptions, delivery system, return policy, product price, flexible delivery system, safety & security, and product advertisements. However, they also encounter various challenges such as difficulty contacting sellers, delivery time changes after transactions, receiving wrong or damaged goods, difficulty changing defective products, unassured product guarantees, long delivery times, complex order processes, privacy information concerns, visual discrepancies, and confusion due to excessive choices.

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